

THE EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE VALUE PROPOSITION ON NORMATIVE COMMITMENT

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Abstract

Organisations continuously seek opportunities to be more productive through the human capital they employ. A firm offering of the employee value proposition (EVP) and understanding of employee commitment could enable organisations to have committed employees that enjoy their work and are oriented towards a growth trajectory. This study sought to examine the effect of the EVP on normative commitment in a parastatal organisation. A quantitative research approach was selected to explore the research objectives. The research instruments comprised of value attributes scale and normative commitment scale. The population sample consisted of employees (N=251). Convenience sampling was used within the context of the study. Descriptive statistics, Factor analysis, Pearson correlation analysis, and Regression analysis were employed to interpret data collected and address the research objectives. A positive relationship between the variables was established. The three EVP factors (work, rewards, and opportunity) positively correlate with normative commitment. Recommendations are made to managers and HR Practitioners regarding the EVP and normative commitment of parastatal employees, which have the potential to employee commitment when implemented. The study provided insights on the factors, affecting EVP and normative commitment. The study also showed the relationship between the variables, enabling management, and HR practitioners to implement strategic interventions to influence employees' normative commitment and EVP experience.

Keywords: employee value proposition, normative commitment, parastatal, work, rewards, opportunity, human resource management.

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1. Introduction

The global work environment is constantly changing due to technological advancements, and organisations have realised that human capital is an essential resource that is pivotal to achieving organisational goals [1]. Organisations continuously strive to ensure that employees remain committed through a compelling employee value proposition [2].

Employees decide to stay and commit to the organisation based on the attractiveness of the benefits, offered by the organisation [3]. Thus, the importance of organisations crafting an EVP package that is attractive to employees leads to job satisfaction, influencing normative commitment. The study, conducted in a parastatal organisation, should clearly define the behaviour they expect from their employees and start using EVP to influence normative commitment. Hence, this study aims to measure the effect of employee value proposition on normative commitment.

Normative commitment can be defined as “the bond that *employees* experience with their organisation, as a result, employees feel connected to their organisation, they feel they fit in and understand the goals of the organisation and how their role fits into the organisation they are ac-

quainted with [4, 5]. This relationship is determined by how the organisation treats its employees. The organisation's employee value proposition for their employees leads to the employees' having a sense of belonging and affiliation. The positive EVP experience leads to enhanced normative commitment. Employees with high normative commitment tend to stay with the organisation due to their loyalty [6]. Employees feel the need to do what they are expected to do, and they feel obligated to remain with the organisation and be productive [7].

Parastatal organisations must understand the importance of EVP. The organisation's EVP are likely to influence the commitment of employees. Employees across the organisation may have different experiences of EVP and related initiatives [2]. The challenges in parastatal organisations negatively affect the employee experience, which influences normative commitment. The lack of a positive EVP experience leads to low employee morale and high turnover [8] and negatively affects productivity. A lack of an attractive EVP may harm normative.

1. 1. Employee Value Proposition

Employee Value Proposition, known as (EVP), can be defined as an offering by an organisation that makes employees feel valued. The aim is to ensure that employees are engaged, productive, and satisfied with their jobs [9, 10]. A well-packaged EVP offering can result in employees feeling motivated and satisfied with their jobs and employers [2611 EVP is the perceived added professional and personal value that employees benefit from their employment within the organisation and includes the different reward features, benefits, and employee advantages, offered to employees [2]. EVP describes the different initiatives the organisation has to implement to make the employees feel valued, i.e. benefits, culture, onboarding [12]. EVP is dependent on the human capital processes that enhance the employee's experience in the organisation, leading to improved productivity [2].

The five attributes have been identified as a base for employers to measure or compile their EVP; namely, i) compensation (financial rewards); ii) benefits (non-financial rewards); iii) career (development and advancement opportunities); iv) work- content (satisfaction and motivation relating to their job characteristics); and iv) affiliation (commitment to and absorption into the work environment). These attributes directly impact the EVP of employees [13]. Compensation, benefits, career development, and advancement opportunities are other extrinsic motivational factors that increase employee morale as employees want to feel valued by them [11]. Work content and commitment to the work environment are intrinsic motivational factors [2]. These attributes positively influence employee commitment [2]. EVP has become the lifeline of many organisations, and EVP attributes, such as compensation, benefits, career development, work content, and advancement opportunities, determine how employees feel about an organisation, whether they feel valued or not [2]. EVP attributes directly impact the experiences of employees within the organisation. When the organisation takes care of the employees' internal and external needs, the loyalty of employees increases, and they feel valued, resulting in high employee morale and increased productivity [11].

1. 2. Normative Commitment

According to [7, p. 6], normative commitment refers to the "moral obligation to continue working for the organisation". Employees remain with the organisation because they have an obligation towards the organisation [7] Recent studies show that normative commitment is experienced due to compliance to organisational policies and procedures [6]. Personal, social, and family values influence employees' loyalty to their affiliated organisations [6]. Normative commitment is strong on employees who feel indebted to the organisation for the opportunities and rewards provided [14, 15]. Normative commitment refers to the individual's connection and identification with the organisation [16].

It is clear, that employers need engaged and committed employees to face the competitive environment ([17], 2011). Furthermore, committed employees form part of a strategic resource

for an organisation. The role of the Human Resources Business Partners (HRBPs) and line management is to ensure that employees are motivated and engaged is now more complex; however, normative commitment can be used as a tool to motivate employees [18].

Employees become loyal to the organisation to the extent that they would do anything to see the organisation strive to its optimum performance level [19]. Employees' loyalty may come from a place of feeling indebted to the organisation because of the opportunities and rewards, provided by the organisation [14]. High normative commitment results in *high job satisfaction* and *low employee retention* (Bothma, 2020). Normative commitment influences employees to willingly behave in a manner that helps achieve organisational goals [20]. Employees who have strong normative commitment feel the need to do the right thing and comply with policies that contribute to the organisation's success [6].

1. 3. Employee value proposition, and normative commitment

Organisations find it challenging to attract and retain key talent, so EVP has become one of the key tools to attract employees and ensure high normative commitment levels [21]. This shows that EVP influences organisational commitment. The advantages of a positive EVP experience are that employees feel that they belong in an organisation, which leads to improved work performance due to increased normative commitment [22]. The EVP experience of employees is one of the determinants of organisational commitment as this is a result of how the employee is treated or feels valued by the organisation [12]. Due to the strong emotional connection, an employee has with the organisation, "who they are" at work is positively influenced [23]. Employees with strong normative commitment feel the obligation to stay with the organisation [7] Sometimes employees stay in the organisation because of their loyalty to the organisation.

The research aimed to establish the relationship between the EVP attributes and normative commitment. The study further investigated which EVP attributes best predicts normative commitment.

2. Materials and methods

2. 1. Research Method

A quantitative approach was selected to address the research objectives. Due to the scientific evidence, the quantitative approach produces objective data (Saunders et al., 2012). The study setting was a parastatal organisation (state-owned enterprise) in South Africa. The permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Chief Executive. This approval was obtained using a written motivation from the student to the Chief Executive. Ethics clearance was obtained from the Industrial Psychology and People Management Research Ethics Committee (IPPMREC). The ethics clearance code is IPPM-2020-407(M). An online survey was employed in this study. Google forms were used. Data were collected over six months (January 2020 to June 2020). Data was analysed based on the online survey responses, provided by participants.

2. 2. Research participants

The population of the study consisted of employees from a parastatal organisation. The size of the population of employees with access to emails is approximately 13 000. All employees with access to emails were requested to participate in this study. Non-probability sampling was used; therefore, all willing respondents had an equal opportunity to participate in the study. Non-probability sampling can be defined as a sampling technique that uses non-randomised methods; for example, participants can be selected due to easy access [24]. Specifically, convenience sampling was used. Convenience sampling can be defined as a sampling technique where a researcher focuses on participants that are available to complete to questionnaire and participants that are easily accessible [24].

The sample comprised of 44.2 % men (n=111), 49.8 % females (n=125) and 6 % other meaning it was unspecified (n=6). Most participants belonged to the Black race group

(n=133; 64.9 %), followed by the Coloured race group (n=37; 14.7 %), Other “unspecified race group” (n=26; 10.4 %), Indian race group (n=19; 7.6 %), Chinese race group (n=4; 1.6 %) and White race group (n=2; 0.8 %). Most participants were employed in the junior category (n= 72; 28.7 %), followed by the senior managerial category (n=65; 25.9 %) and the Trainees (n =52; 20.7 %).

2. 3. Measuring instruments

In terms of *Measuring instruments*, the online survey consisted of two sections, biographical information was requested in the first section and the second section, participants were requested to complete the measures EVP (The Value Attributes Scale, developed by Ferreira, 2016), and normative commitment (normative commitment scale, developed by Meyer and Allen, 1991).

Employee Value Proposition Scale

In terms of the *Employee value proposition scale*, the value attributes scale is a twenty-item measure of dimensions remuneration and benefits, organisational culture, career development, work content, and work-life balance. The items are scored on a 5-point frequency scale, ranging from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important), and include statements, such as: “To what extent are you provided with challenging targets?”; “To what extent do you have supportive and like-minded colleagues?”; and “Are you satisfied with your employer’s provision of incentive bonuses/variable pay?”. [3] reported acceptable Cronbach’s alpha coefficients for the overall scale as .71.

Normative Commitment Scale

Normative commitment scale is a six-item scale. The items are scored on a 5-point frequency scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), and include statements, such as: “I do not feel any obligation to remain with my organization”; “Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave”; and “I would feel guilty if I left this organization now”. [7] reported an acceptable Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.73 for normative commitment.

2. 4. Statistical analysis

Data were analysed using SPSS software, version 27. Descriptive statistics summarise the data and allow the researcher to compare collected data numerically [25]. This study obtained descriptive statistics for all items for the different scales used. Factor analysis was computed to ensure validity. Principal component analysis (PCA) was used to reduce the dimensions of datasets, making it easy to interpret data collected [25]. Principal Axis Factoring (PAF) was used to simplify datasets by creating a valid factor solution. Inferential statistics were used to make predictions based on the data. The Pearson correlation analysis measured variables’ existence and stability relationship [25]. According to [25], a correlation of 1.0 suggests a perfect relationship between the variables irrespective of the direction of the relationship. Regression analysis was performed to examine the relationship between EVP, and normative commitment.

2. 5. Ethical Considerations

Adherence to ethical considerations is of great importance when the study involves different participants and the university’s reputation. The ethics committee assessed the feasibility of the study to obtain ethical clearance and ensure adherence to the university’s ethical standards. Due to the nature of the study, data was be treated with confidentiality, and respondents remained anonymous. Respondents completed an informed consent, which noted that participation is voluntary and that they can withdraw from the study at any time, without any negative consequences. The researcher ensured that data were represented accurately, truthful, and honest. Data was stored in a password-protected computer file, to which only the researcher and the supervisors have access. The data’s privacy and confidentiality were communicated to the respondents, and they were informed that data would be used for research purposes only.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive analysis for employee value proposition is provided in **Table 1**. The mean values ranged from 3.90 to 3.70. This implies that employees' EVP experience may be positive. Standard deviation ranged from 0.70 to 0.80. Most variables within the employee value proposition achieved acceptable Cronbach alphas that ranged from 0.79 to 0.81, it was noted, that organisational culture achieved a lower Cronbach alpha of 0.60. Career development achieved a value below 0.70. Dimensions with a small number of items (under 10), such as career development, in this case, yield lower reliability scores. Hence, it is essential to assess the mean inter-item correlations. By assessing the mean inter-item correlations, we can confirm the internal consistency of the measure. Upon inspection of the mean inter-item correlation, the value achieved was 0.25 within the cut-off point of 0.40 [25].

Table 1

Descriptive analysis for EVP

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis	alpha
RB	3.90	0.70	0.48	-1.71	6.51	0.80
OrgCul	3.75	0.62	0.39	-2.93	14.35	0.60
CD	5.24	1.04	1.07	-2.24	7.93	0.79
WC	3.84	0.85	0.72	-1.72	4.59	0.92
WLB	3.70	0.80	0.64	-1.61	4.80	0.81

Table 2 provides analysis of normative commitment. The mean achieved was 3.22, the standard deviation was 0.64. This suggests that employees are likely to be committed to the organisation due to the moral obligation towards the organisation.

Table 2

Descriptive analysis for normative commitment

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis	alpha
NC_com	3.22	0.64	0.41	-0.96	0.89	0.76

Factor Analysis

The EVP scale was subjected to the Principal Axis Factoring (**Table 3**) with Oblimin with Kaiser Normalisation rotation method. Upon the first iteration, items 10 and 15 yielded communalities below 0.30 and therefore were not suitable and were removed. According to [25], communalities must be monitored to check how much of the variance in each item is explained. Values lower than 0.30 could indicate that the item does not fit well with other components. Upon the second iteration, the correlation matrix revealed the presence of communalities above 0.30. The Keyser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value achieved was 0.89, exceeding the recommended value of 0.60, as suggested by [25]. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity reached statistical significance, supporting the factorability of the correlation mix. There were no clear loadings, so a forced three-factor solution was presented. The Eigenvalue of 1.15 for three factors was revealed, and these factors explain a cumulative variance of 59.19 %. [25] states that factor loading above 0.40 is acceptable. Principal axis factoring extracted three factors with all the items, loading above 0.40. The Cronbach's alphas for work were 0.91, and 0.86 for rewards, and 0.81 for an opportunity. Therefore, a three-factor solution was accepted: work accounting for 46.92 % variance, rewards accounting for 8.08 % variance, and opportunity accounting for 4.18 % variance.

Table 3
Factor analysis for EVP

Items	Factor			
	1 Work	2 Rewards	3 Opportunity	Communal- ities
EVP1_RB1 Recognition, provided to you by your employer e.g. Financial recognition, such as cash paid travel.			0.41	0.34
EVP2_Ocul1 The extent, to which your employer respects differences in race, gender and age.			0.54	0.50
EVP_3CD1 The opportunities, offered to you by your company for learning and career development outside of your current job e. g. sabbaticals, coaching, mentoring, leadership training.			0.76	0.64
EVP_4CD2 The opportunities, offered to you by your company for career advancement e.g. job advancements/promotions, internships and apprenticeships with experts, internal job posting.			0.90	0.75
EVP_5WC1 The quality of performance feedback and performance discussions you have had with your supervisor	0.81			0.70
EVP_6WC2 The extent, to which you believe your contribution and work is valued.	0.89			0.81
EVP_7WC3 The level of challenge and interest you derive from your job.	0.93			0.69
EVP_8WC4 The extent, to which you are provided with challenging targets.	0.72			0.63
EVP_9WLB1 Having a manageable workload and reasonable work pace.	0.53			0.53
EVP_11CD3 The opportunities, offered to you by your company for training within your current job e.g. skills training.	0.58			0.47
EVP_12WLB3 The extent, to which your employer supports a balanced lifestyle (between your work and personal life).	0.54			0.59
EVP_13WLB4 Your employer's provision of work/life programmes, such as flexible working arrangements, flexible hours.	0.59			0.59
EVP_15Ocul3 The degree, to which your employer encourages and organises team building or other social networking activities amongst employees.	0.69			0.54
EVP_16Ocul4 Your employer's provision of employee health and wellness programmes e.g. Employee Assistance Programmes, counselling services, fitness centres.		0.34		0.31
EVP_17RB2 The provision of competitive pay package (i.e. basic salary plus benefits, allowances or variable pay)		0.78		0.61
EVP_18RB3 Your employer's provision of medical aid, retirement and pension benefits.		0.70		0.56
EVP_19RB4 Your employer's provision of incentive bonuses/variable pay.		0.93		0.78
EVP_20Ocul5 The provision of recognition via non-financial means e.g. certificates of recognition		0.70		0.62
Eigenvalue		1.15		
Variance	46.92	8.08	4.18	
KMO			0.89	

Normative Commitment

The normative commitment scale was subjected to Principal Component Analysis. The correlation matrix revealed the presence of 0.30 and above commonalities for all items. **Table 4**

shows the Keyser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value achieved was 0.84, exceeding the recommended value of 0.60, as suggested by [25]. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity reached statistical significance, supporting the factorability of the correlation mix. The Eigenvalue of 3.116 was revealed, explaining the variance of 62.32 %. The Cronbach alphas yielded was 0.74. The loading for the normative commitment component was above 0.40, and a one-factor solution was accepted.

Table 4
Factor analysis for Normative commitment

Items	Component	
	Normative Commitment	Communalities
COM3NC I owe a great deal to my organisation.	0.813	0.661
COM7NC I would feel guilty if I leave my organisation.	0.833	0.694
COM11NC I would not leave my organisation right now because I have a sense of obligation to its people.	0.750	0.562
COM14NC I do <i>not</i> feel any obligation to remain with my current employer.	-0.669	0.447
COM15NC The organisation deserves my loyalty	0.867	0.752
Eigenvalue	3.116	
Variance	62.327	
KMO	0.84	

Correlation Analysis: EVP and Normative Commitment

In terms of the correlations between the variables in **Table 5** below, the following was interpreted: Work is positively correlated to normative commitment ($r=0.323$, $p<0.001$), with medium size effect. Rewards are positively correlated to normative commitment ($r=0.130$, $p<0.001$) with small size effect. Opportunity is positively correlated to normative commitment ($r=0.227$, $p<0.001$) with small size effect.

Table 5
Correlation analysis for EVP and Normative Commitment

Variables	EVPF1 Work	EVPF2 Rewards	EVPF3 Opportunity	NCNEW Normative Commitment
EVPF1 Work	1	0.716**	0.763**	0.323**
EVPF2 Rewards		1	0.658**	0.130*
EVPF3 Opportunity			1	0.227**
NCNEW Normative Commitment				1

Regression Analysis: EVP and Normative Commitment

A significant regression equation was found $F(3,244)=13.42$, $p<0.000$). **Table 8** indicates that the total variance, explained in the model, is 14.2 %. Multicollinearity was not presented as the tolerance value that ranged from 0.342 to 0.400. According to [25], common cut-off tolerance values of less than 0.10 may indicate the presence of multicollinearity. The variance inflation factor (VIF) ranged between 2.499 to 2.926. These values were lower than the cut-off value of above 10, as suggested by [25]. Therefore, multicollinearity was not of particular concern. Therefore, the beta (β) values can be interpreted with confidence.

Table 6 indicates that work contributed the largest variance to normative commitment recording the highest beta value ($\beta=0.47$; $p<0.000$). Rewards yielded the second largest beta value of ($\beta=-0.19$; $p<0.000$). Opportunity yielded the least variance, recording the beta value of ($\beta=0.02$; $p<0.000$). Work and rewards had a significant prediction on normative commitment. Opportunity did not predict normative commitment.

Table 6
Regression analysis EVP on Normative Commitment

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta						Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	2.299	0.282		8.144	0.000	0.376	0.142	0.131		
EVPF1 Work	0.440	0.094	0.473	4.661	0.000				0.342	2.926
EVPF2 Rewards	-0.198	0.090	-0.191	-2.201	0.029				0.467	2.144
EVPF3 Opportunity	0.023	0.105	0.020	0.215	0.830				0.400	2.499

4. Discussion

4.1. Descriptive statistics- EVP and normative commitment

EVP dimensions are remuneration and benefits, organisational culture, career development, work content, and work-life balance. After the data analysis, the following results were obtained for the *Employee value proposition*, Career development obtained the highest mean of 5.24. This indicates that most employees realised that the organisation offered career development opportunities. This is a good indication as employees tend to be motivated and highly engaged when they feel that the organisation cares for their growth [8]. The mean for remuneration and benefits obtained was 3.90. This indicates that most employees perceived that the organisation offered excellent remuneration and benefits. The remuneration and benefits element is part of the employee lifecycle and directly impacts employee commitment and EVP experience [2]. The mean for work content was 3.84. Work content refers to the activities that a job is made up of [19]. Employees perceived work content to be enriching and challenging. Employees' commitment increases when they feel that their work is valued [27]. The mean for organisational culture obtained was 3.75. This indicates that employees perceived the organisational culture to be average. Work-life scored a mean of 3.70. This indicates that most employees perceived that the employer supports a balanced lifestyle between work and personal life. According to [28], employees need good working relationships with like-minded colleagues to be engaged and committed.

The mean value achieved for *normative commitment* was 3.22. This indicates that employees are likely to be committed to the organisation. This is further indicated by [6], confirming that normative commitment positively influences the quality of work, performed by the employees. Employees with high normative commitment remain loyal to the organisation and are more likely to behave in a way that helps the organisation to succeed [29].

An exploratory factor analysis was carried out on the three variables, the EVP scale were subjected to Principal Axis Factoring, and normative commitment was subjected to principal components analysis. The exploratory factor analysis indicates the interrelationship between variables and each variable's influence on other variables [30]. EVP showed a three-factor loading, and the three new variables for EVP were created: work, rewards, and opportunity. Work yielded a variance of 46.92 %. Rewards yielded a variance of 8.08 %. Opportunity yielded a variance of 4.18 %. The Cronbach's alphas for work were 0.914, and 0.858 for rewards, and 0.813 for the opportunity, this indicated that the new variables were reliable. These new variables were renamed by categorising the elements, measured in the EVP scale, and it is aligned to the current research on EVP as suggested by [30]. Employees believe that they are valued by the organisation when there is flexibility, allowing for work-life balance [31]. This shows that the one-factor solution can explain all other variables. Normative commitment showed a factor of one total explained variance of 62.32 %.

4.2. The relationship between EVP dimension and Normative commitment

Pearson correlation analysis was used to address the main research objective of what is the relationship of employee value proposition on normative commitment. In response to the research

question, the analysis showed a relationship between EVP and normative commitment. Work, a factor of EVP, has a medium effect on normative commitment. The value employees feel due to their work impacts normative commitment [32].

Rewards also had a small correlation with normative commitment. This supports the results of [6] who argue that normative commitment is not primarily influenced by the offerings the organisation provides, but this type of commitment is influenced by the individual's moral obligation to obey the rules and policies of the organisation. Opportunities had a small correlation with normative commitment. This supports previous studies that have confirmed that normative commitment is not directly linked to opportunities and benefits [6].

Regression analysis for EVP predicting normative commitment

A regression analysis was conducted to identify the prediction in the influence between employee value proposition, and normative commitment. The results showed that work, a factor of EVP, largely influenced normative commitment. This indicates that work, a factor of EVP, had a significant prediction on normative commitment. Challenging work and a manageable workload directly influence normative commitment [6]. Rewards also predicted normative commitment. Previous studies show that normative commitment is not influenced by the rewards, offered by the organisation [29]. However, the findings in this study show that rewards influence normative commitment. This is very interesting as normative commitment is deemed to be loyalty due to an obligation to the organisation [7] The employees could feel obligated to the organisation because of the rewards and other offerings, enhancing their loyalty. There was no significant prediction of normative commitment on the opportunity.

Limitations of the study. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, most employees worked from home, limiting employee access and negatively affecting the quantity of data collected. It is essential to highlight the psychological impact the coronavirus pandemic had on people, affecting the way people view life, economic uncertainty, loss, and grief, this could have influenced the interest they had in participating in this study. There are limited existing studies on normative commitment.

Recommendations and managerial implications. The findings in this study show that employees' EVP experience is reasonable within the organisation. EVP offerings play an essential role in the motivation of employees within the organisation [21]. Employees that remain motivated also have a strategic fit with the organisation [32]. Human resources practitioners should emphasize the importance of EVP in the employee lifecycle. They should also conduct awareness sessions with the line managers on the importance of EVP and consistent implementation of the EVP offerings within each department. During the onboarding phase employees need to decide whether they will commit to the organisation or not. EVP is one of the factors, influencing new employees to either commit to the organisation or not [34]. New employees consider how the organisation values them and that becomes part of their motivating factors [34]. It is recommended, that managers are consistent and fair when it comes to providing opportunities for their employees; for example, all the employees should be given equal opportunity to attend training and should be treated the same way by the managers.

It is important to note, that some EVP factors did not significantly contribute to the prediction of normative commitment. The findings in this study show that work contributed to the prediction of normative commitment. Employees remain committed to the organisation because of the "psychological contract" and feelings of obligation towards the organisation [14]. Furthermore, rewards and opportunity EVP factors did not have a significant contribution towards the prediction of normative commitment, this may have been a result of the dissatisfaction of employees about the rewards and opportunity EVP offerings. It is recommended, that human resources practitioners ensure that rewards and opportunity elements of the EVP are consistently applied across the organisation. For example, implementation of the financial and non-financial rewards programme, which has a clear and transparent point system and reward levels. This will force the line managers to be objective, resulting in employees feeling empowered and in control of the rewards programme.

Organisations must value employees as they are the most important asset in the organisation. The employer can give different attractive offers to their employees. This can be presented within the EVP package. Hence, employees would be able to relate to and find this beneficial. This

will ensure a positive employee experience and employee engagement [11]. The EVP can include different training opportunities for employees, performance-based rewards and recognition, and employee wellness programs

When it comes to normative commitment, [7] it indicate that employees are likely to have a normative commitment in an organisation that shares the same values as theirs, and [14] further stipulate that due to high normative commitment employees then feel morally obligated to stay with the organisation. The aforementioned studies support the findings of this study, which indicate that EVP have a significant contribution towards the prediction of normative commitment in an organisation.

It is recommended, that during the attraction phase, HR practitioners should focus on the fit between the candidate and the organisation, they should understand the values of the candidates and how those values will fit in with the values, norms, and culture of the organisation. The pre-screening requirements should look at the skills and experience to determine the candidate's competence, and the requirements should include an analysis of the individual behaviour, their values, and how that would fit into the organisation. Managers should ensure that the organisations' values are consistently implemented within their departments; the employee experience should not depend on the manager's personality but the values of the organisation.

The pandemic has impacted how work is performed, and has implications on how employees perceive their work, the value they feel, and the motivation to work for their organisations. HR practitioners as change champions should ensure that change is managed effectively to prevent employee disengagement, organisations must remain true to their values and have a defined focus on employee wellbeing.

Recommendations for future research. There is scant research on EVP, and normative commitment. Therefore, insights, provided in this study, can assist future researchers to use the results and findings discussed to further the research on employee value proposition and normative commitment. Qualitative studies will assist in building a narrative on EVP dimensions, needed by employees.

5. Conclusion

Studies on EVP and normative commitment are scant. The current study sheds light on dimensions of the EVP that can ensure employees remain committed to the organisation, with a focus on normative commitment. The findings in this study show that EVP impact normative commitment. Human resource practitioners must remain cognisant of these attributes and ensure their implementation and offering within the EVP. The use of a compelling EVP has the potential to increase normative commitment and, as a result, could positively affect employee performance, therefore, increasing the productivity of the parastatal organisation.

References

- [1] Koekemoer, E. (2014). An explorative study on factors influencing the career success of management employees. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 40 (2). doi: <http://doi.org/10.4102/sajip.v40i2.1204>
- [2] Paadi, K., Barkhuizen, N., Swanepoel, S. (2019). Exploring the building blocks of an employee value proposition for graduate interns. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanity Studies*, 11 (1), 51–67.
- [3] Ferreira, E. (2016). *The role of Employee Value Propositions and Corporate Brand Preferences in Talent Attraction*. University of Cape Town.
- [4] Saunders, M., Lewis, P., Thornhill, A. (2012). Understanding research philosophies and approaches to theory development. *Research Methods for Business and Students*, 122–161. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/309102603_Understanding_research_philosophies_and_approaches
- [5] Sen, C. E. M. (2018). The Effects of Positive Psychological Capital on Employees Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, and Ability Coping With Stress. *Journal of Academic Research in Economics*, 9 (2), 164–184.
- [6] Betanzos, N., Paz, F. (2016). Benefits of Normative Commitment for Organizations. *Psychological Studies*.
- [7] Allen, N. J., Meyer, J. P. (1990). The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63 (1), 1–18. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8325.1990.tb00506.x>

- [8] Grossmeier, P. T, Terry, J. (2014). Measuring a Broader Value Proposition: Capturing the Connections Between Health, Well-Being and Performance. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 28 (4), 10–13.
- [9] Mahajan, A. (2019). Relationship of Talent Management with Organizational Culture: A Discussion Paper. *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 54 (3), 471–482.
- [10] Heger, B. (2007). Linking Employee Value Proposition (EVP) to Employee Engagement and Business Outcomes. Preliminary finding from a Linkage Research Pilot Study. *Organisation Development Journal*, 25, 121–132.
- [11] Reddy, S. (2017). Employee value proposition: A Morale Booster. *Humancapitalonline.Com*, 34–36.
- [12] Smith, A. (2011). Employee value proposition. *Black Circle*.
- [13] Browne, R. (2012). Employee value proposition. *Beacon Management Review*, 2, 29–36.
- [14] Mokhtar, R., Azwa Ambad, S. N., Syed Annuar, S. N., Lajuni, N. (2021). Employee Engagement and Its Relationship Towards Normative Commitment in Malaysia Oil and Gas Industry. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 11 (1), 164. doi: <http://doi.org/10.5296/ijhrs.v11i1.18260>
- [15] Odoardi, C., Battistelli, A., Montani, F., Peiró, J. M. (2019). Affective Commitment, Participative Leadership, and Employee Innovation: A Multilevel Investigation. *Revista de Psicología Del Trabajo y de Las Organizaciones*, 35 (2), 103–113. doi: <http://doi.org/10.5093/jwop2019a12>
- [16] Dhanpat, M. N. (2017). Evaluating organizational commitment of call centre agents. Paper session presented at the Pan Pacific Conference.
- [17] Adeoye, M. (2008). Emotional Intelligence and self-efficacy as determinants of academic achievements in English language among students in Oyo State Senior Secondary Schools. Unpublished Work, University of Ibadan.
- [18] Al-Jabari, B., Ghazzawi, I. (2019). Organizational commitment : A review of the conceptual and empirical literature. *International Leadership Journal*, 11 (1), 78–119.
- [19] Aksoy, C., Şengül, H. I., Yilmaz, Y. (2018). Examination of the relationship between job satisfaction levels and organizational commitments of tourism sector employees: a research in the southeastern anatolia region of Turkey. *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 17 (65), 356–365. doi: <http://doi.org/10.17755/esosder.343032>
- [20] Chughtai, A., Zafar, S. (2017). Antecedents and consequences of organizational commitment among Pakistani university teachers. *Pakistan Economics and Social Review*, 55 (2), 391–414.
- [21] Wahba, M., Elmanadily, D. (2015). Employer Branding Impact on Employee Behavior and Attitudes Applied Study on Pharmatecual in Egypt. *International Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 4 (6), 145–162. doi: <http://doi.org/10.18488/journal.11/2015.4.6/11.6.145.162>
- [22] Machin, M. A., Fogarty, G. J., Bannon, S. F. (2009). Predicting Employees ' Commitment To and Support for Organisational Change. *The Australian and New Zealand Journal of Organisational Psychology*, 2 (3), 10–18. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1375/ajop.2.1.10>
- [23] Arasanmi, C. N., Krishna, A. (2019). Employer branding: perceived organisational support and employee retention – the mediating role of organisational commitment. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 51 (3), 174–183. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1108/ict-10-2018-0086>
- [24] Parveen, H., Showkat, N. (2016). Non probability and probability sampling. Unpublished Work, 1–9.
- [25] Pallant, J. (2011). *SPSS Survival Manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using SPSS*. Australia: Allen & Unwin
- [26] Brook, J., Aitken, L., Webb, R., MacLaren, J., Salmon, D. (2019). Characteristics of successful interventions to reduce turnover and increase retention of early career nurses: A systematic review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 91, 47–59. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2018.11.003>
- [27] Veleva, V., Bodkin, G., Todorova, S. (2017). The need for better measurement and employee engagement to advance a circular economy: Lessons from Biogen's "zero waste" journey. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 154, 517–529. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.03.177>
- [28] Watson, I., Buchanan, J., Campbell, I., Briggs, C. (2019). What do people want from work? *Air and Space Power Journal*, 20–28.
- [29] Bothma, M. (2020). The effect of affective and normative commitment on helping behaviour in different online contexts. *SA Journal of Information Management*, 22 (1). doi: <http://doi.org/10.4102/sajim.v22i1.1190>
- [30] Wehman, P. (2017). Experimental Rigor in Rehabilitation Research: Fact or Fantasy? *Journal of Rehabilitation*, 2–6.
- [31] Venkataramani, S. (2021). Make Way for a More Human-Centric Employee Value Proposition. Available at: <https://www.gartner.com/smarterwithgartner/make-way-for-a-more-human-centric-employee-value-proposition>
- [32] Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., Xanthopoulou, D. (2019). Job Demands-Resources theory and the role of individual cognitive and behavioral strategies. *The Fun and Frustration of Modern Working Life: Contributions from an Occupational Health Psychology Perspective*, 94–104.

- [33] Lees, D., Dhanpat, N. (2021). Relationship between manager credibility, strategic alignment and employee motivation. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 19. doi: <http://doi.org/10.4102/sajhrm.v19i0.1517>
- [34] Ashley, C. (2018). Internal and External Factors That Influence Employee Retention. *Educator Multidisciplinary Journal*, 1 (1), 86–102.

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